

Review Of Music Inheritance Of Nanyang Major Key Tune, Henan Province

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Abstract

This paper mainly starts from the music of Henan Nanyang major key tune, reviews the relevant literature through the CNKI platform, and uses the literature review method and induction method to collect, sort out and classify the literature of the Henan Nanyang major key tune studied by scholars and so on. The article mainly starts with the analysis of the academic literature trend of major key tunes, academic literature analysis of major key tunes, and "inheritance of school education and music culture".

Introduction

In Nanyang, the major key tune is one of the main songs in Henan. The major key tune, originally called "Drum song", was first seen in Kaifeng, and was originally divided into Zhoukou, Yuxian County, and Nanyang. Two branches, Houyu County and Nanyang, gradually merged in the process of development. After being introduced into Nanyang, Guziq absorbed some ditty, opera tunes and folk song tunes from Shaanxi, Sichuan, and Hubei, both in content and form, and finally formed major key tunes with local characteristics, which were mainly distributed in the Nanyang area and widely popular throughout Henan. After the 1930s, it was extremely popular in the Nanyang area. Later, influenced by a variety of factors, the grand tune declined in the Central Plains, only preserved and prosperous in the Nanyang area, so it is also called the "Nanyang Grand tune".

Nanyang's major key tune is developed from folk music, poetry, and legends. Throughout Nanyang area, is one of the important types of rap music in the Nanyang area, has a history of hundreds of years, has a profound accumulation of quyi, and is a relatively ancient art form. It is popular in Nanyang folk, unique Nanyang local characteristics, singing form is Nanyang dialect, with strong local flavor, and a simple style, both elegant and popular, in the Nanyang area received the crowd welcome; the national instrumental music three strings, pipa, guzheng, moon, dulcimer, falling hu, erhu, hu (soft bow jinghu), dong xiao, etc. Among its percussion instruments, the hand plate and octagonal drum are two essential, with distinctive characteristics of Henan music. The major key tunes have preserved a considerable part of the vulgar songs of the Ming and Qing dynasties, and have both north and south ditty, with many song cards. Its singing cards contain folk songs, Kunqu Opera, Huang, Qinqiang Opera, and other opera cards. These precious cultural heritages are of great value to the study of popular literature since the Ming and Qing dynasties, and to the local opera, music history, quyi music, and aesthetics.

With the importance of national attention to intangible cultural heritage, on June 7, 2008, the tune of a major key tune was included in the second batch of the national intangible cultural heritage protection list. The ancient art form of major key tune music was gradually picked up, and then the excavation of its historical origin, artistic form, cultural connotation, inheritance, and protection began.

As one of the excellent carriers of Chinese traditional folk music, the Nanyang major key tune, along with the progress and development of the society, like other traditional cultures, also cannot escape the criticism brought by multicultural music. It is also marginalized and slowly fades out of people's vision. Therefore, it is an important task and challenge to find multi-channel inheritance channels in parallel. Based on this problem, we can explore the research results of previous people, hoping to open up a new path of inheritance.

research status quo

At present, because of Nanyang's major key tune regional, its academic achievements are concentrated in China, this research relies on the CNKI resources database platform, through the theme search "major key tune".The literature is relatively few, includingmajor key tune research papers 49, major key tune research

dissertation 6; theme search "school education music culture inheritance" academic papers 150 (core 24), and "school education music culture inheritance" thesis 52 papers (data until November 2022). After academic combing, the author found that most of the existing achievements are focused on artistic form research and inheritance and protection suggestions, and there is relatively little comprehensive research on the inheritance practice and school inheritance practice at the social level. The academic achievements related to this paper are analyzed as follows:

(1) Analysis of academic literature trend in Nanyang major key tune

This study works through the network, the city book literature room, and second-hand book reviews. According to the consulted data display, the Book section has 9 related literature. The earliest works involving major key tunes were those published by Mr. Zhang Changgong (1948); Journal papers (Table 1) have 49 related documents, The earliest academic paper involving major key tunes is the paper "Preliminary Exploration of major key tunes" published by Zhong Libin (2003) and the paper "Introduction and rise and Fall of Nanyang major key tunes" published by Wang Songyang (2003); The dissertation (Table 2) has 6 related documents. The first master's thesis on major key tunes was the master's thesis "Study of Dengzhou major key tunes in Cultural Vision" published by Luo Jie (2015) and the master's thesis "Study of Rhyme in Nanyang major key tunes" published by Chen Fengjuan (2015). Up to now, I have found no doctoral dissertation on major key tunes (see Table 1 and Table 2 for details) .

Table 1 Statistics of major key tune academic papers (drawn by the author)
(49 as of November 2022)

Academic Paper (Year)	Quantity: Number of academic papers (year): quantity		
2003	2	2015	4
2005	1	2016	1
2006	3	2017	5
2007	2	2018	3
2008	3	2019	2
2010	2	2020	4
2011	2	2021	8
2012	3	2022	3
2014	1		

Source: CNKI

Table 2 Statistics of the dissertation of tune research in a major key (drawn by the author)
(Total 6 articles, as of November 2022)

Academic Paper (Year)	Quantity: Number of academic papers (year): quantity		
2015	2	2019	1
2018	1	2020	2

Source: CNKI

The above table 1, table 2 more clearly shows Henan Nanyang's major key tune field of academic papers and dissertation publishing trend, since 2008 after the national "intangible", based on the increase year by year, rebound slightly, shows that the major with Henan Nanyang tune related research, more and more attention.

(2) Analysis of academic literature in major key tunes

The existing achievements are sorted out and classified according to the research surface. The historical origin, circulation, rise and fall, artistic characteristics, inheritance, and development of Nanyang's major key tunes in Henan Province are described as follows:

(1) Discussion on the origin of major key tunes

First, in terms of books, there are 5 earlier works on the discussion of the origin and historical evolution of major key tunes. Zhang Changhong (1948) published "drum song" and Zhang Changhong (1986) published "Zhang Changhong collection", xinxiu, changxi (1983) compiled "key", Nanyang regional culture bureau (1990) "Chinese folk music integration Nanyang volume", Henan people's publishing house (1994) published Nanyang regional folk art. Since the formation of the major key tune at that time, its inheritance method depended on the form of oral teaching, and the relative lack of ancient documents at that time, the historical origin of the major key tune was in the situation of "still uncertain". Despite this, the former people still combed the historical development of major key tunes, and made a lot of comparisons and analyses in various historical periods, to infer the historical origin of major key tune tunes. These works have made useful enlightenment and great contributions to discussing the historical origin of major key tunes.

Second, in the aspect of journal papers, the first journal on the origin of the tune is by Zhong Libin (2003), the author compared the relationship between the tune and the related songs, inferred that the tune and fork, octagonal drum, is the origin of the Ming and Qing dynasties; the li Haimeng (2006) paper "tune into Nanyang time test", through case analysis, argues that the tune came into Nanyang through the Chinese official rotation

training system and business road in the middle Ming to early Qing dynasty. Feng Binbin (2006) argues that the Origin and Artistic Characteristics of Henan major key tune emphasize that a major key tune is an art form formed from the middle Ming to Qing Qianlong; Li Haimeng (2012) draws the time of major key tune formation.

It is not difficult to find that researchers consult a large number of relevant historical materials, collect and sort out, and collect the songs and songs of each historical period. During the reign of Emperor Qianlong of the middle leaf of the Ming Dynasty and the Qing Dynasty, it mainly evolved from the mutual fusion of "Bianliang minor song" and "fork song". These achievements are of great academic value for the historical origin of Nanyang's major key tune in Henan Province. It not only provides a relevant theoretical source for this paper but also enhances the author's further understanding of the source of the music of Nanyang's major key tune in Henan Province.

(2) The rise and fall of major key tunes

First, the book is written, Xin Xiu and ChangXi (1983) "major key tune" records, introduces the beginning of the major key tune, accompanied by national culture and business, gradually spread to Henan, to the late qing dynasty to the early republic of China, the major key tune is still popular, and began to decline is after the "May 4", there are many reasons.

Second, the journal paper, wang Songyang (2003) the Nanyang major tune rise and fall, from the introduction of major key tune formation, evolution, in the development of the Nanyang region and protection and research of these four aspects, analyzes the rise and fall, after the "May 4 ", other mainstream music has declined, while Nanyang major music repertoire in the gradual evolution and innovation, the content gradually rich, artistic charm.

Thus, after the May 4th Movement, people gradually understood and accepted new cultures, new ideas, and new ideas in the process of social development, and their life also underwent great changes. In addition, due to the criticism of multicultural music and the constantly changing factors of people's aesthetic concepts, the ancient art form of major key tune music has been diluted by people, gradually divorced from the public view of the people, rapidly showing the trend of decline and confused development prospects, which is not optimistic (the exception of Nanyang area). These existing results present the true portrayal of the social development of the author at that time and increase the author's understanding of the rise and fall of the major key tunes circulating at that time.

(3) The artistic characteristics of major-key tunes

First, in terms of books, recorded by Raymond Zhou and Yan Tianjin (2004) in ▪ Major in Nanyang Region, 229 major key tunes were collected and were widely influenced at that time; Zhu Jingxiu (2003) emphasized that the art form.

second, Journal papers, Li Hongbin (2005), in his article "A Brief Analysis of the Songs in Henan Major Major", analyzes the head song in Henan major, And from the content, composition structure, composition techniques, playing Musical Instruments and other aspects, he analyzes the reasons for the uniqueness of the artistic value of Henan Bantouqu; Li Haimeng (2006), in " On the Characteristics of Henan major key tune —— and On the Classification of three-string Performance styles, discusses the theoretical knowledge of three-string playing for historical reasons is limited to the accompaniment, However, the three-string playing style in Henan major key tune is always elegant, Performance techniques are mainly based on verve, From the three aspects of the performance environment, performance techniques and aesthetic characteristics of the head song in major key tune, To fully explain the artistic charm of the three-string accompaniment; Liu Liyuan (2017), in his paper "On the Accompaniment of Songs in Henan major key tune", To analyze the accompaniment instruments, accompaniment forms and playing style of Henan major key tune, Thus explore the position of these accompaniment instruments in Henan major key tune.

Third, the dissertation, Chen Fengjuan (2015) in his master thesis "Nanyang major key tune rhyme research", its fundamental requirement is the rhyme of the text, with 531 examples; Zhu Zengshuai (2018) in his master thesis "Nanzhao major key tune research" stressed that Nanzhao is the art of rap, is a combination, its novel lyrics, complex, from the origin, music form, artistic value and inheritance, and protection to analyze.

Through the combing of the above literature, it is learned that the major key tune is embodied in its unique style structure, singing music, form in performance, language rhyme, and accompaniment instruments, because of its unique musical style and artistic characteristics. Its curvature structure has two single forms and set forms, according to the needs of the repertoire. The accompaniment instruments are mainly three-string pull instruments, which can play the door music before opening the singing or play the instrumental music alone. The music style of the major key tune is elegant and simple, sung in the Nanyang dialect, which has strong Henan cultural characteristics and extremely strong regional color. It is rich, compatible, and profound. These existing achievements are of great value in academia and have a certain enlightenment significance to the author in exploring the connotation of local music and culture.

(4) Inheritance and development of major key tunes

In this regard, For example, in Wang Dan (2007), in his paper "The Phenomenon of Folk Inheritance in Nanyang major key tune", The group inheritance of Nanyang major key tune is widely used in the folk, Tell about its inheritance process and analyze its causes; Zhang Yanling (2010), "A New Way to explore the Intangible Cultural Heritage Protection, Inheritance and Development of —— Nanyang major key tune into our University Student Classroom", pointed out that, First, analyze the problems in the inheritance of major key tunes, Then I summarize the positive significance of the major key tune into the classroom, And initially explore its new ways of inheritance and development; Sun Li (2012), in his paper "The Evolution and Inheritance of the Nanyang major key tunes of the Intangible Cultural Heritage", On the development course of Nanyang major key tune, Summarize how to inherit and protect the key tune; Zhou Liqing (2015) pointed out in his paper "Nanyang Quyi —— under the Protection of" Intangible Cultural Heritage "Taking" Nanyang tune in Grand tune "as an example", In the past 30 years, the inheritance of Nanyang major key tune tunes has been incomplete and broken, With the introduction of various policies, major key tune music ushered in a new development look, But the actual situation is not optimistic; Malili (2016) in his paper "Henan major key tunes can be inherited and developed is research", To the characteristics of Henan major key tune with cultural "specimen", Exploring its essence and cultural connotation, And find out new ways to develop; Hao Fang (2017), in his paper "Research on the Development Strategy of Songs in Nanyang major key tune", According to the development status of Nanyang Grand tune, Discussed how Nanyang Grand tune was inherited and developed, Hope to provide suggestions and suggestions for the future development of Nanyang major key tune for reference; Wang Renya (2017), in his paper "Research on the Historical Inheritance and Development Path of Songs in Henan Major Music", Reviewing the results of previous studies, Field research was carried out, The relevant paths in the inheritance are proposed, To provide a basis for the future research in the field of traditional art; Jiang Han (2018), in his paper "On the Artistic Characteristics, Inheritance and Development of Songs in Henan major key tune", Through the research, practice, and investigation of professional tunes, Analyze and explain its ontology characteristics. Highlighting its artistic charm, Hope to get more attention, Make it get better inheritance and development; In Hu Zhenyu (2019), "The Development Dilemma and Rescue Inheritance of Nanyang Major key tunes under the Intangible Cultural Heritage Vision", from the four aspects of artistic characteristics, historical changes, current situation and rescue inheritance of major key tunes, To analyze its development status quo; Wang Yu (2020), in his paper "Huang Tianxi's Works <Funeral hua> Interpretation of the Inheritance and Innovative Development of major key tunes", Interpretinterprets the inheritance of classics and artistic innovation of the major key tune of "Burying Flowers", Huang Tianxi, innovative creative and performance techniques, Shape a new "Daiyu burial flower", Will better inherit the big tunes.

As can be seen from these academic results, major-tune music, as a kind of rap music in southwest Henan province, has a long history and once flourished in the Central Plains. In the development process of major key tune, in its evolution and innovation, constantly bring the new, is widely spread, and constantly spread in the surrounding areas. However, with the change of the inheritance group, the inheritance and development of major key tunes have been out of touch. Such as the serious aging of inheritors, young people, and lack of school education inheritance. At present, these difficulties are urgent for the introduction of relevant national policies, the support of relevant government departments, and the attention of school education. It is necessary to protect old artists, cultivate a new generation of inheritors, combine local characteristic culture with schools, increase the inheritance and practice of traditional folk music in schools, improve the school curriculum system, and put forward new inheritance measures and strategies in the process of inheritance and development. These urgent problems provide important ideas and references for this study.

(3) Analysis of the academic literature trend of "School education and music culture inheritance"

Through the National Knowledge Network of China (CNKI), the theme was searched for "School education and music Culture Inheritance", involving 150 articles on academic papers, including 24 core journal papers; 52 degree papers, including 7 doctoral papers and 45 master papers (all data until November 2022). As shown in Table 3 and Table 4:

Table 3 Academic papers (core) statistics on School Education and Music Culture Inheritance (drawn by the author)

(Total of 150, including 24 core papers by November 2022)

Academic Paper (Year)	Quantity: Number of academic papers (year): quantity		
1996	1	2013	4
1999	1	2014	2
2003	1	2015	2
2004	1	2016	1
2006	1	2017	1
2008	1	2018	4
2011	1	2021	1
2012	1	2022	1

Source: CNKI

Table 4 Statistics of dissertations on the Inheritance of School Education and Music Culture (drawn by the author)

(A total of 52 papers, including 7 doctoral papers and 45 master's papers, as of November 2022)

Academic Paper (Year)	Quantity: Number of academic papers (year): quantity
2007	1 2015 4 (1 Doctor)
2008	1 2016 6
2009	1 2017 7 (2 Ph.D.)
2010	2 2018 8 (2 Doctor)
2011	5 2019 6
2012	4 (1 Ph.D.) 2021 1
2013	1 2022 1
2014	4 (1 Dr.)

Source: CNKI

First, the journal papers. By Fan Zuyin (1996), The main task of the school is to inherit the national culture, The author expounds it from three aspects of teaching content, teaching method and "bilingual" teaching; Feng Guangyu (2003), in his article "Ethnic Music Culture Inheritance and School Music Education", First, according to the relevant national plans, Then, through the specific case analysis, To bring four practical strategies for sustainable inheritance; Zhang Yiwen (2015) in his Research on the Inheritance and Protection of School Music Education and the Traditional Folk Music Culture, Traditional folk music culture in the teaching, Further reforms are needed, We should set up the mainstream concept of traditional folk music education, Thus promoting the progress of Chinese folk music; Fan Yutao (2018) emphasized in his "On the Inheritance and Communication of School Education and Intangible Cultural Heritage, ——, Taking Qiang Traditional Music School Education as an example", With the progress of the society, The Qiang ethnic group's intangible cultural heritage is facing difficulties, The author analyzes and discusses it with specific examples, Put forward his own opinion.

Second, is the dissertation aspect. Zhang Yinghua (2012), Research on Miao Music Communication in Guizhou under the Background of Globalization, The spread of contemporary Miao music in Guizhou, Using the multi-disciplinary comprehensive analysis method, From the analysis at different levels, And in view of the various problems and difficulties shown, Relevant cultural strategies and action strategies are proposed]; Bo Yajie (2017) pointed out in his paper "Research on the Development of School-based Textbooks for the Inheritance of Ethnic Music Culture", The important music culture inheritance field of school education, To take the development of school-based teaching materials as the focus and action choice, Based on the theoretical level, Carry out practical inheritance in school education; Han Yanting (2018) "Research on Primary School Folk Song Teaching under the threshold of Ethnic Music Culture Inheritance" emphasizes, School music education is a living text of the inheritance of folk music culture, With primary school folk song teaching as the main theme, Combined with the function of music education itself, Provide conditions and guarantee for its inheritance, And cultivate students' sound personality and the necessary guarantee of all-round development; Lin Qing (2018) proposed in his paper "Theoretical Exploration of the Construction of Regional Music Education System under the Non-genetic Vision", From the perspective of "intangible cultural Heritage", Pour regional music into the music classes of various schools in Longyan area, And provides a new theoretical structure for the construction of regional music education system.

Through the analysis of the above literature, it can be seen that school education has great significance in inheriting traditional folk music, which can stimulate the students' identification and sense of belonging to the national culture and can better cultivate the student's interest in the traditional Chinese culture, which carries forward the important inheritance and practice function. However, there are also some problems, such as the lack of feasible inheritance and promotion plan in the specific implementation, and the lack of its educational implication. These academic achievements can inspire the writing ideas of this paper and provide space for the research of this paper.

2. Research content and methods

(1) Research content

On the basis of the previous research results, With General Secretary Xi Jinping's important discourse on "carrying forward the fine traditional Chinese culture", To inherit and inherit the excellent traditional Chinese culture as the research background, To look through the music body of Nanyang major key tune, The inheritance of Nanyang major key tune music represented by the excellent traditional culture of music in the school education and social education level is taken as the research object, Adhering to the methodology of combining theory with practice, Guided by the relevant theories of educational anthropology, ethnomusicology and sociology, and the ontology of the inheritance of intangible cultural heritage, Make full use of field survey methods, literature review methods, multidisciplinary methods, case study methods and other research methods,

Connecting the history and the present situation, In the specific spatiotemporal context, Dig out the contemporary values, moral concepts, humanistic spirit and educational values contained in the Nanyang major key tune, After a lot of field investigation, field investigation, etc., To further understand the way and content of Nanyang major key tune inheritance in school and society, Finding out the difficulties faced in the transmission process, and their causes, And put forward the countermeasures to solve the problem. Finally, the educational significance and value of Nanyang's major key tune music inheritance system in contemporary times are summarized.

(2) Research methods

1. Fielding method

Nanyang's major key tune is the traditional culture of Nanyang and a typical representative of Nanyang folk culture. It has been developed from folk music, poetry, and legends. Throughout the Nanyang area, is one of its many forms of rap, has a history of hundreds of years, has a profound accumulation of folk art, and is a relatively ancient art form. It is popular in Nanyang folk, unique Nanyang local characteristics, with the form of Nanyang dialect singing, showing the authentic local flavor, has a simple style, with a typical regional nature, field investigation has become the data source and research method of this paper.

2. Literature review method

Based on the topic of this paper, the relevant literature concentrated in China, this paper through the domestic major network platform and books, literature reference room for the domestic-related research results of the search and consult, the research-related literature material unified sorting and summary, to the use of theoretical knowledge and research methods to comb and induction.

3. Multi-disciplinary approach

Nanyang's major key tune is a comprehensive art form, which integrates the art forms of rap and instrumental music.

Its historical origin and cultural implications involve sociology, culture, pedagogy, ethnomusicology, and other related disciplines, so the multi-disciplinary method has become the main research method of this study.

4. Case analysis method

The inheritance of Nanyang's major key tune in the Nanyang area mainly comes from the protection units, professional troupes, inheritors, academic research institutions and friends, etc. Due to its scattered inheritance area, two professional colleges and troupes in Nanyang city were selected as individual cases in this study, so the case analysis method is an important means to investigate and analyze the current situation of tunes in Nanyang's major key tune.

3. conclusion

Throughout the existing research, it can be found that many scholars have formed a relatively clear research structure in the singing, accompaniment, and inheritance research of Nanyang major key tune, Henan Province, and have achieved practical and available research results. The research results provide a reference for theoretical basis and practical reference for this research and also provide a reference for the current situation and problems of school education inheritance and how to solve the problems.

At present, although the tune of Henan Nanyang major has achieved a wide range of research results, there are also many shortcomings in the music culture of the tune of Nanyang major of Henan Province and the practice of inheritance in schools. At present, the inheritance theory system formed in the school is imperfect and not mature. The existing achievements are mostly reflected in the music form, inheritance, and protection, and the analysis is relatively generalized. The content of the article is mainly based on text narration, lack of specific data and legend analysis, and lack of certain in-depth scientific and theoretical research. The research level of Nanyang's major key tune in Henan Province mostly focuses on the journal papers published by music teachers in colleges and universities in the region and the dissertation of master students with local students. These articles are limited by the length of the literature, and they need to further expand the depth and breadth of the research, and they also lack depth and specificity in the countermeasures to be solved.

This study will be based on the characteristics of traditional music itself, learn from anthropology, folklore, education, and other discipline backgrounds, comprehensive adoption of a variety of research methods involved in this paper, combined with various channels of inheritance resources, maximize the coordination, to achieve the combination of music and culture, inheritance practice, and for Henan Nanyang tune art complement in theory in the future development.

In line with the inheritance and development of national folk music, in line with the development of hometown music and love, plus as a local has unique advantages, can better and more conveniently explore the tune and the symbiotic relationship between local national culture, the hometown precious traditional art more specific, hope to let more people more comprehensive understand the survival of the intangible cultural heritage, cause the government attention and the social people from all walks of life, to more comprehensive protection, transmission and inheritance, and development of Nanyang tune.

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